

Appendix A: Semi-structured interview script

Intro

- About myself and the project
- Information sheet and consent form
- Is it ok if I record the interview
- Feel free to elaborate on any details that come to mind
- How much time do you have?

Relationship with personal wellbeing/health

- How old are you?
- How would you describe your attention to your personal health?
- Are you paying attention to something or taking specific actions to prevent future problems? Why/why not?

Use of quantified self

- What do you use already? (voluntarily)
 - If several, do you ever wish they were integrated?
- What are you looking to find out?
- Do you look back in time at past data?
- Positive aspects
- Negative aspects / Fears
 - Have you ever found out negative information?
- Have you ever considered buying a specific tool? (ex: fitbit)
- Have you ever discovered some data you didn't think you had tracked (ex: steps per day on your phone)?
- Do you ever get the same data multiple days in a row?
- Do you ever measure anything related to your internal health (not exercise)?
- If you had a magic quant self device, what would it measure?
- Have you got an app on your phone, would you mind showing me?

Quantified self in relation to other people

- Did you ever think about tracking someone else?
- Would you ever consider measuring the health of your child?
- Do you ever share the information with other people?

Device

- Urine analysis can tell you many things about your well being. Let's say you have a device to check what is in your urine, how would you imagine it?
- Two scenarios
 - Something that was in your toilet? Or something more like a pregnancy test?
- Who else uses your bathroom?
 - Visitors
 - Cleaning
 - Aesthetic

Finish

- Thank you for your time!

- Can you explain a bit about your role at La Source?
- How much experience do you have with urine analysis?
- Hospital context
- Care home context - experience with older people
- Home context